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A Constant Elasticity of Variance - Based Stochastic Modeling Approach to Oando Plc's Equity Price Fluctuations

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the application of Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) models in evaluating the financial performance of two distinct Oando Plc investment portfolios. By employing Ito's lemma, we derive precise analytical conditions for modeling and estimating the capital position of corporate investors, thereby demonstrating the utility of the CEV framework in capturing stock market dynamics. Closed-form empirical solutions are obtained for each investment case, offering insight into the behavior of Oando's asset valuation under varying market influences. The analysis further examines the impact of time on stock price behavior, the influence of return rates on investment value, and the role of volatility in assessing portfolio risk. Comparative evaluation of the two proposed models is conducted, with validation through statistical normality testing. The results provide actionable insights for strategic investment planning and risk assessment within Oando Plc's financial operations.

Key words: Stock Market, Constant Elasticity of Variance, Stochastic Model, Stock Price, Stochastic Differential Equation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The stock market comprises buyers and sellers of stocks, which represent ownership claims in businesses. It includes various exchanges and trading venues where shares of publicly held companies are bought and sold. The legal framework that facilitates these financial activities is known as the stock exchange. Trading occurs either through institutionalized formal exchanges or over-the-counter (OTC) platforms, both governed by a set of defined regulations. However, stock prices are inherently unstable, seasonal, time-dependent, and highly volatile—making them difficult to predict. This volatility is largely attributed to uncertainties stemming from natural disasters, global economic trends, and socio-political policies, all of which can have unforeseen effects on the demand and supply of stocks [1]. Because of this, investors now have to go beyond studying the company's history, performance and development prospects of such fundamentals, but also be familiar with the variety of technical analysis in order to win a huge return on investment and become a successful investor. Stock trend analysis plays an important role in practical stock trading. One of the best options is to choose stocks by fundamental analysis and then confirm when to buy and sell stocks by technical analysis. Hence, the need for stochastic analysis through the appropriate model.

In analyzing stock trends, there are various tools which can be used depending on the factors that shape the stock price trends, and stochastic analysis include the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) model which was introduced to effectively compliment one of the limitations of Stochastic Differential Equation

(SDE). Cox noticed the fact that constant volatility was unrealistic; a power law relationship between the asset's volatility and its price levels. This offers more realistic and flexible way of modeling time-varying volatility for investors or owner's corporation. More so, this CEV model can also be twisted by incorporating mean-reverting properties into the volatility process. This results in the Modified Constant Elasticity of Variance (MCEV) model, which allows for better handling of both short-term and long-term fluctuations, thereby making it more robust and suitable for varying market conditions. In all, the usefulness of CEV are as follows: by the use of CEV equation, corporate investors can better understand the volatility of their investments and make more informed decisions about risk management; the CEV equation can be used to help corporate investors optimize a mix of investments with varying levels of volatility and returns and finally understanding the patterns of volatility over time, corporate investor can make more informed decisions about when to buy and sell investments.

All the same, due to the instability on the value of wealth of corporate investors in respect stock market prices which is linked as stochastic formation. For that reason, the applications of CEV and MCEV equations were adopted.

In this study, we considered CEV and MCEV equations in assessing the wealth of four different corporate investors and describing the behavior of a security's volatility over time which was not considered by previous efforts. Precise conditions were given to illustrate the effectiveness of the systems. Each investment solutions suggest distinctive perception on CEV dynamics of assessing wealth of corporate investors. This paper extends the work of [2] by incorporating probability parameters in one of CEV and MCEV equations which can better balance investor's portfolios by selecting a mix of investments with different levels of risk and returns.

Constant Elasticity of Variance Models for the Analysis

[3] looked at two Stochastic Differential Equation models in finance such as the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) and the Black-Karasinski term structure models. They made use of the explicit finite difference method for Partial Differential Equations in the numerical experiments and it was observed from the study that the Partial Differential Equations for the valuation of Option price utilizing the riskless portfolio method completely removes the stochastic component from the Stochastic Differential Equation, which makes it easier to obtain the solution of the resultant PDE. In addition, making use of published data from the Nigerian Stock Exchange, numerical experiments revealed that as the price of the stock price or underlying asset and risk-free interest rate increases, the value of the option decreases.

[4] considered the option pricing implications of the CEV model in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), [5] had an empirical study of the CEV model using data from NSE and discovered that CEV model gives a reasonable representation of stock returns. [6] analysed option pricing and Greeks under the Modified Constant Elasticity of Variance (MCEV) model with stochastic volatility. Details of CEV and MCEV can be in the following papers such as [7], [8],[9], etc.

Stochastic Models for the Analysis of Stock Market Prices

[10] while studying a stochastic analysis of stock price variation assessments in OandO Nigerian, PLC, applied stochastic analysis of Markov chain on the closing of stock price data of OandO Nigerian, PLC. (2017-2021); by transforming the stock prices into 3-steps transition probability matrix solution for each independent year. The analytic solution of stochastic analysis indicated that the closing stock price of 2017 had the highest mean rate of returns of 2.4112 and growth rate of 69%. The 2018 stock price had the best probability of price not changing in the near future: 26%. The impact of future price changes was also evaluated and the outcome revealed that various levels of pricing effects on the aspect of percentage increase and decrease as it affects the original prices. [11] examined the problem of system of stochastic differential equation of time varying investments of Dangote Cement PLC, where multiplicative inverse effects, additive effects, additive inverse effects were applied as key parameters in the model to obtain stock rate of returns. They adopted Ito's theorem and solved the problem analytically and obtained four different investment solutions. [12] considered the differential and stochastic differential equations of time varying investment returns and obtained precise conditions which govern asset price return rates through multiplicative and multiplicative inverse trend series. The analysis of the proposed model

revealed that the multiplicative inverse trend series is efficient and reliable than the multiplicative trend in both deterministic and stochastic systems. Also, [13] studied the stochastic analysis of stock market expected returns for investors and considered the detailed conditions for obtaining the drifts, volatilities and variances of four different stocks. The variances of the four different stocks were compared, applying their criteria for selection and the result obtained showed that stock1 was the best among the stocks of different companies, which agrees with the work of [14]

The plan of this paper is set as follows: Section 1 presents Introduction, Section 2 presents Purpose of the paper, Section 3 presents Mathematical Preliminaries, Section 4 presents Problem Formulation, Section 5 presents Analysis and Results.

2. Purpose of this Paper

Develop and apply mathematical models—specifically the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) equations—to analyze and compare the financial performance, risk, and investment dynamics of two different capital portfolios within Oando Plc.

3. Mathematical Preliminaries

To understand the stochastic model, we define the following in which the study hinges:

Definition 1: Σ -Algebra: Let Ω be a non-empty set and let \mathcal{F} be a collection of subsets of Ω . Then \mathcal{F} is said to be a σ -algebra if

- i) $\emptyset \in \mathcal{F}$
- ii) given that a set $A \in \mathcal{F}$ then the complement of A i.e., $A^c \in \mathcal{F}$,
- iii) whenever the sequence $\{A_i\} \in \mathcal{F}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots$, then $\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \in \mathcal{F}$

Definition 2: Probability Measures: Let Ω be a non-empty set and let \mathcal{F} be a σ -algebra of subsets of Ω . Then a function that assigns every set $A \in \mathcal{F}$ to a number in $[0, 1]$ is called a probability measure \mathbb{P} . For this case we denote by $\mathbb{P}(A)$ the probability of A and it is such that;

- i) $\mathbb{P}(\Omega) = 1$
- ii) if A_1, A_2, \dots is a sequence of disjoint sets in \mathcal{F} then $\mathbb{P}(\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{P}(A_n)$

The pair (Ω, \mathcal{F}) is called a measurable space while the triple $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is called a probability space

Definition 3: Stochastic Processes: Mathematically, a stochastic process may be defined as a collection of random variables which are ordered in time and defines at a set of time points which may be continuous or discrete.

Definition 4: Constant Elasticity of Variance: This is an equation that describes the behavior of a security's volatility over time. It is based on the assumption that the volatility of a security's returns is not constant, but rather follows an exponential growth pattern.

Definition 5: Stochastic Differential Equation: A Stochastic Differential Equation is a differential equation with stochastic term. Therefore, assume that $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ is a probability space with filtration

$\{f_t\}_t \geq 0$ and $W(t) = (W_1(t), W_2(t), \dots, W_m(t))^T, t \geq 0$ an m -dimensional Brownian motion on the given probability space. We have SDE in coefficient functions of f and g as follows

$$dX(t) = f(t, X(t))dt + g(t, X(t))dZ(t), 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

$$X(0) = x_0,$$

Where $T > 0$, x_0 is an n -dimensional random variable and coefficient functions are in the form $f : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $g : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. SDE can also be written in the form of integral as follows:

$$X(t) = x_0 + \int_0^t f(S, X(S))dS + \int_0^t g(S, X(S))dZ(S)$$

Where dX, dZ are known as stochastic differentials. The \square^n is a valued stochastic process $X(t)$.

Theorem 1: (Ito's lemma). Let $f(S, t)$ be a twice continuous differential function on $[0, \infty) \times A$ and let S_t denotes an Ito's process

$$dS_t = a_t dt + b_t dz(t), t \geq 0,$$

Applying Taylor series expansion of F gives:

$$dF_t = \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_t} dS_t + \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_t^2} (dS_t)^2 + \text{higer order terms (h.o.t)},$$

So, ignoring h.o.t and substituting for dS_t we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} dF_t &= \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_t} (a_t dt + b_t dz(t)) + \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_t^2} (a_t dt + b_t dz(t))^2 \\ &= \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_t} (a_t dt + b_t dz(t)) + \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_t^2} b_t^2 dt, \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial S_t} a_t + \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S_t^2} b_t^2 \right) dt + \frac{\partial F}{\partial S_t} b_t dz(t) \end{aligned}$$

More so, given the variable $S(t)$ denotes stock price, and hence, the function $F(S, t)$, Ito's lemma gives:

$$dF = \left(\mu S \frac{\partial F}{\partial S} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial S^2} \right) dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial F}{\partial S} dz(t)$$

The details of the above concepts can be seen in [18-19] respectively.

4. Formulation of the Problem

We consider stochastic systems imposed with the dynamics of stock quantities which is said to have a complete probability space (Ω, F, \wp) such that a finite time investment horizon $T > 0$.

Hence, the system of Constant Elasticity of Variance equation and its modifications are given as follows:

$$dX_1(t) = \mu X_1(t) dt + \sigma S^\beta X_1(t) dZ^{(1)}(t)$$

$$(1) dX_2(t) = \mu(1 - \theta) X_2(t) dt + \sigma S^\beta X_2(t) dZ^{(2)}(t) \tag{2}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} X_1(0) &= X_0, X_2(0) = X_0, \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3}$$

where, $X_1(t), X_2(t)$, are asset prices, The expression dZ , which contains the randomness that is certainly a characteristic of asset prices is called a Wiener process or Brownian motion. β represents elasticity parameter of the risky assets, S is the price process of the stock market under modified CEV, and σ are volatility of the stock market.

4.1 Method of Solution

We implement the methods of Ito's lemma in solving for $X_1(t), X_2(t)$ To seize this problem we note that we can forecast the future worth of the asset with sureness.

From (3.1) Let $f(X_1, t) = \ln X_1$ so differentiating partially gives

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial X_1} = \frac{1}{X_1}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial X_1^2} = -\frac{1}{X_1^2}, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} = 0 \tag{4}$$

Following Ito's lemma, we gave;

$$df(X_1, t) = \sigma S^\beta X_1 \frac{\partial f}{\partial X_1} dZ(t) + \left(\mu X_1(t) \frac{\partial f}{\partial X_1} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 X_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial X_1^2} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) dt \quad (5)$$

Substituting (4) into (5), gives;

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sigma S^\beta X_1 \frac{1}{X_1} dZ(t) + \left(\mu X_1(t) \frac{1}{X_1} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 X_1^2 \left(-\frac{1}{X_1^2}\right) + 0 \right) dt \\ &= \sigma S^\beta dZ(t) + \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) dt \end{aligned}$$

Integrating both sides, taking upper and lower limits, gives;

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t d \ln X_1 &= \int_0^t df(X_u, u) = \int \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) du + \int_0^t \sigma S^\beta dZ(t) \\ \ln X_1 - \ln X_0 &= \left(\mu u - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 u \right) \Big|_0^t + (\sigma S^\beta Z u) \Big|_0^t \\ \ln \left(\frac{X_1}{X_0} \right) &= \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) t + \sigma S^\beta Z(t) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Taking the ln of the both sides, gives;

$$X_1(t) = X_0 \exp \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) t + \sigma S^\beta Z(t) \quad (7)$$

From (2) Let $f(X_2, t) = \ln X_2$ so differentiating partially, gives

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial X_2} = \frac{1}{X_2}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial X_2^2} = -\frac{1}{X_2^2}, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (8)$$

According to Ito's gives

$$df(X_2, t) = \sigma S^\beta X_2 \frac{\partial f}{\partial X_2} dZ(t) + \left(\mu(1-\theta) X_2(t) \frac{\partial f}{\partial X_2} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 X_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial X_2^2} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) dt \quad (9)$$

Substituting (8) and (9) into (2), gives;

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sigma S^\beta X_2 \frac{1}{X_2} dZ(t) + \left(\mu(1-\theta) X_2(t) \frac{1}{X_2} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 X_2^2 \left(-\frac{1}{X_2^2}\right) + 0 \right) dt \\ &= \sigma S^\beta dZ(t) + \left(\mu(1-\theta) - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) dt \end{aligned}$$

Integrating both sides, taking upper and lower limits, gives;

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t d \ln X_2 &= \int_0^t df(X_2, u) = \int \left(\mu(1-\theta) - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) du + \int_0^t \sigma S^\beta dZ(t) \\ \ln X_2 - \ln X_0 &= \left(\mu(1-\theta) u - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 u \right) \Big|_0^t + (\sigma S^\beta Z u) \Big|_0^t \\ \ln \left(\frac{X_2}{X_0} \right) &= \left(\mu(1-\theta) - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) t + \sigma S^\beta Z(t) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Taking the ln of the both sides, gives the following close form solution of SDE.

$$X_2(t) = X_0 \exp\left(\mu(1-\theta) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)t + \sigma S^\beta Z(t) \tag{11}$$

5. Analysis and Results

This section presents the analyzed results derived from the methods outlined in Section 4.1, implemented using MATLAB software:

Table 1: Evaluation of Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) model under varying return rates, presented with the corresponding solution and parameter values.

$X_0 = 10.65, \sigma = 0.2, S = 0.75, \beta = 0.55, \beta = 0.3, z(t) = 1$

X_0	Return rates(μ)	$X_1(t)$	Return rates(μ)	$X_1(t)$	Mean $\bar{X}(X_1(t), X_1(t))$
10.65	0.1	11.7042	1.1	183.2897	97.4969
9.90	0.2	13.5077	1.10	195.1011	104.3044
10.35	0.3	15.4249	0.9	185.6231	100.5240
8.30	0.4	13.5247	0.8	52.8451	33.1849
9.00	0.5	16.0494	0.7	29.9750	23.0122
12.50	0.6	24.4154	0.6	24.4154	24.4154
14.00	0.7	29.9750	0.5	16.0494	23.0122
22.50	0.8	52.8451	0.4	13.5247	33.1849
72.00	0.9	185.6231	0.3	15.4249	100.5240
68.90	0.10	195.1011	0.2	13.5077	104.3044
58.90	1.1	183.2897	0.1	11.7042	97.4969

Table 2: Modified Constant Elasticity of Variance (MCEV) model incorporating a probability term, evaluating the effects of varying return rates with the corresponding solution and parameter values:

$X_0 = 10.65, \sigma = 0.2, S = 0.75, \beta = 0.55, \beta = 0.3, z(t) = 1, \theta = 0.5$

X_0	Return rates(μ)	$X_2(t)$	Return rates(μ)	$X_2(t)$	Mean $\bar{X}(X_2(t), X_2(t))$
10.65	0.1	12.9716	1.1	118.2783	65.6249
9.90	0.2	12.6763	1.10	131.6117	73.6440
10.35	0.3	13.9319	0.9	130.8257	72.3788
8.30	0.4	11.7453	0.8	38.8891	25.3172
9.00	0.5	18.5956	0.7	23.0175	20.8066
12.50	0.6	19.5490	0.6	19.5490	19.5490
14.00	0.7	23.0175	0.5	18.5956	20.8066
22.50	0.8	38.8891	0.4	11.7453	25.3172
72.00	0.9	130.8257	0.3	13.9319	72.3788
68.90	0.10	131.6117	0.2	12.6763	72.1440
58.90	1.1	118.2783	0.1	12.9716	0.003157

Table 3: Evaluation of the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) model under varying trading times, along with the corresponding solution and parameter values:

$X_0 = 10.65, \sigma = 0.2, S = 20.5, \beta = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, z(t) = 1,$

X_0	Time (t)	Return rates (μ)	Volatility (σ)	$X_1(t)$
10.65	1	0.5	0.2	22.5573
10.65	2	0.5	0.2	36.4543
10.65	3	0.5	0.2	58.9128
10.65	4	0.5	0.2	95.2076
10.65	5	0.5	0.2	153.8625
10.65	6	0.5	0.2	248.6533
10.65	7	0.5	0.2	401.8423
10.65	8	0.5	0.2	649.4071
10.65	9	0.5	0.2	1049.4902
10.65	10	0.5	0.2	1696.0544

Table 4: Analysis of Modified Constant Elasticity of Variance (MCEV) model evaluating the impact of trading time variations, using the given solution and parameter values:

$X_0 = 10.65, \sigma = 0.2, S = 20.5, \beta = 0.1, \beta = 0.1, z(t) = 1,$

X_0	Time (t)	Return rates (μ)	Volatility (σ)	$X_2(t)$
10.65	1	0.5	0.2	17.5677
10.65	2	0.5	0.2	22.1106
10.65	3	0.5	0.2	27.8284
10.65	4	0.5	0.2	35.0249
10.65	5	0.5	0.2	44.0823
10.65	6	0.5	0.2	55.4828
10.65	7	0.5	0.2	69.8297
10.65	8	0.5	0.2	87.8877
10.65	9	0.5	0.2	110.6154
10.65	10	0.5	0.2	139.2206

Table 5: A comparative analysis of CEV and MCEV asset values under fixed return rates and volatility, with varying trading durations.

X_0	Time (t)	Return rates (μ)	Volatility (σ)	$X_1(t)$	$X_2(t)$
10.65	1	0.5	0.2	22.5573	17.5677
10.65	2	0.5	0.2	36.4543	22.1106
10.65	3	0.5	0.2	58.9128	27.8284
10.65	4	0.5	0.2	95.2076	35.0249
10.65	5	0.5	0.2	153.8625	44.0823
10.65	6	0.5	0.2	248.6533	55.4828
10.65	7	0.5	0.2	401.8423	69.8297
10.65	8	0.5	0.2	649.4071	87.8877
10.65	9	0.5	0.2	1049.4902	110.6154
10.65	10	0.5	0.2	1696.0544	139.2206

5.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

An analysis of Tables 1 and 2 indicates a general upward trend in the growth rate, which corresponds to an increase in asset valuation. This is consistent with financial theory, where growth serves as a fundamental determinant of an asset's expected future cash flows. Specifically, higher growth rates suggest an increase in earnings generation capacity, thereby elevating the present value of future cash flows. Conversely, a decline in the growth rate reflects diminished earnings potential, resulting in a reduction in the present value of future returns. This relationship is particularly evident in columns 3 and 5, where variations in the growth rate correspond with changes in projected asset valuations. Such trends are critical in investor behavior, as firms exhibiting sustained growth are typically more attractive to investors, whereas declining growth may lead to diminished investment interest.

Tables 3 and 4 underscore the influence of the time value of money on investment outcomes. The findings demonstrate that the duration over which an investment is held significantly affects its value appreciation. However, due to the discounting effect of time, the impact is nonlinear. While longer holding periods allow for compounding returns, they simultaneously subject future earnings to greater discounting, thereby moderating the net present value. This dual effect highlights the complexity of time as a factor in investment valuation.

In Table 5, the asset values presented in columns 5 and 6 provide insight into the company's market position and valuation status. The higher asset values in column 5 suggest that Oando is a mature firm with a robust market presence and competitive strength. In contrast, the comparatively lower asset values in column 6 may indicate that the firm is undervalued by the market. This undervaluation could represent a potential opportunity for risk-tolerant investors seeking capital gains. The same interpretation holds for the corresponding mean asset values, further reinforcing the distinction between established valuation and perceived market mispricing. These observations are instrumental for strategic decision-making, offering a data-driven perspective on financial performance and investor perception.

5.2. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated approximate analytical solutions to the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) equations by formulating two distinct systems of CEV models. Closed-form solutions were derived to assess and compare the capital performance of two Oando investment structures. Through empirical analysis, the asset values of the company were examined using the solutions of the proposed models. The influence of time on stock market behavior and its subsequent impact on asset valuation was explored. Furthermore, the role of return rates in quantifying investment performance, as well as the effect of stock price volatility in evaluating associated investment risk, were systematically analyzed. The comparative results from both models were subjected to statistical validation using a normality test, confirming the reliability of the proposed approaches in modeling and analyzing asset values.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

- I. While the present study focused on the Constant Elasticity of Variance (CEV) and Modified Constant Elasticity of Variance (MCEV) models, future research is encouraged to explore related stochastic frameworks such as Stochastic Differential Equations (SDEs) and Modified Stochastic Differential Equations (MSDEs) for broader comparative insights.
- II. It is recommended that future investigations incorporate the stock prices of three or more companies to enhance the generalizability and robustness of empirical findings.
- III. The application of hypothesis testing techniques, particularly through Snedecor's F-distribution, is strongly recommended for comparing asset values across different investment cases, as it provides a statistically rigorous basis for evaluating differences in asset behaviour.

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